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Oncogene activation during TNBC resistance.

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We describe here activation of oncogenes during. Described oncogene activation was prominent and included induction of *Pvt1*, *Pim3* and *Myc*. ETS family factors were also activated including *ETV5* and *ELK4*.

Citations

1. Tseng, Y.Y., Moriarity, B.S., Gong, W., Akiyama, R., Tiwari, A., Kawakami, H., Ronning, P., Reuland, B., Guenther, K., Beadnell, T.C. and Essig, J., 2014. PVT1 dependence in cancer with MYC copy-number increase. *Nature*, 512(7512), pp.82-86.